

The role of halogens in on-surface Ullmann polymerization

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Abstract

Ullmann coupling is the most common approach to form surface-confined one- and two-dimensional conjugated structures from the derivatives of haloaryl molecules. The dimension of the formed nanostructures can be controlled by the number and location of halogens within the molecules. This study illustrates the role played by the specific halogen choice in the design, orientation, and extent of the surface-confined organometallic and polymeric nanostructures. A study of five 1,4-dihalobenzene molecules, containing chlorine, bromine, and iodine was performed on Cu(110) by scanning tunneling microscopy, fast-X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, and near edge X-ray absorption fine structure techniques. Our experimental data identify different molecular structures, reaction temperatures and reaction kinetics depending on the halogen type. Climbing image nudged elastic band simulations further unveil this effect by providing distinctive diffusion path for each halogen. We demonstrate that, besides the structure of building blocks, the halogen type should be taken into account for the design of surface-confined polymeric structures based on Ullmann coupling.

Introduction

The discovery of graphene with its remarkable high charge mobility, thermal, mechanical, and optoelectronic properties highlights the greatest breakthrough of this decade in materials science.¹⁻⁴ However, graphene's lack of a bandgap limits its application as semiconductor in electronic devices, which has stimulated a growing interest to synthesize organic analogues of graphene.⁵⁻⁸ One of the most compelling strategies in this arena is to design surface-confined fully-conjugated polymers with tunable bandgaps based on rational choice of monomer.⁹⁻¹² The flexibility of organic synthesis offers a broad playground for creating two-dimensional (2D) conjugated polymers by exploring various surface reactions using different building blocks.¹³⁻¹⁵ Surface-confined 2D polymers are produced through bottom-up methodologies which result in large molecular structures generated from small monomers.⁹ The presence of the surface permits the production of ordered 1D¹⁶ or 2D¹⁷ polymeric structures suppressing an entropically-driven disorder of solution synthesis. In addition to passive templating, the surface can also act as a catalyst accelerating the reaction and guiding the orientation of the growing polymer structure.¹⁸ Although it is relatively easy to obtain long-range order in molecular self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) which are driven by weak interactions, this is rarely the case for covalently bound structures, due to the irreversible nature of covalent coupling. A possible approach to form long-range ordered covalent networks is to pre-order the monomers in a self-assembled network and to subsequently covalently cross-link these monomers into a polymer structure. This could be achieved using a multi-step reaction, in which the monomers first form a dynamic intermediate which self-assembles in a 2D monolayer and then the neighboring molecules undergo a coupling reaction irreversibly linking them in a covalent structure.¹⁹, [Basagni2014] In fact, the most popular reaction used in on-surface chemistry, Ullmann coupling, expresses these features: it is a two-step process in which the transition metal supporting substrate catalyzes²⁰ the dehalogenation of arylhalide precursors, forming an organometallic (OM) intermediate¹⁶ which subsequently couples into covalent structure via new C-C bonds.²¹ Both steps are temperature dependent,¹⁸ with the activation energy being dependent on the particular molecule²² and the particular surface.^{23,24} On Cu and Ag surfaces, the deposited molecules can dehalogenate at room temperature and form an OM intermediate of the reaction that is stable up to the polymerization temperature.²⁵⁻²⁷

While the majority of recent studies on surface-confined Ullmann coupling has focused on understanding the structure and order of the polymers on different substrates²⁴ and the density of defects,²⁸ little attention has been paid to the effect of the halogen byproduct. A few theoretical¹⁸ and experimental^{29,30} studies have reported the dissociation of halobenzenes on a metallic surface, addressing the differences in the adsorption energies. However, the possible effects of halogen on the reaction outcome were not explored. The derivatives of 1,3,5-tris(4-bromophenyl)benzene functionalized with bromine (TBB),^{23,31} iodine (TIB)²² and both the halogens (TBIB)²⁷ have been studied on different surfaces, but a coherent comparison to reveal the effect of the halogens was not reported. The contribution of halogens in the formation of 1D polymers *via* Ullmann coupling has been recently reported,^{25,26} showing that the halogens are part of the OM unit cell after deposition of 1,4-dibromobenzene (dBB) on Cu(110). These studies also illustrate that the structures obtained from dBB²⁵ and 1,4-diiodobenzene (dIB)¹⁶ on Cu(110) are different, which further emphasizes the importance of studying the halogens and the processes that transform the intermediate phase into a polymeric structure.

Since the first report describing on-surface Ullmann coupling,³² several studies have provided insights into its reaction mechanism and kinetics.^{20,21,33} A kinetic model based on a combined experimental and theoretical approach was applied to the polymerization of dBB on Cu(110), showing that the polymerization follows a nucleation-and-growth mechanism.³⁴ However, there are still open questions regarding both the fundamental understanding and the practical realization of on-surface Ullmann coupling. For example, how does one design a precursor and reaction conditions to maximize the long-range order and minimize the defect density in the polymer structure?³⁵ Here, we report a systematic study of five different 1,4-dihalobenzene molecules, a phenyl ring containing two

halogens (Cl, Br or I) on Cu(110). Our findings illustrate the role of halogens, despite being a by-product, in determining the structures of the formed ordered π -conjugated polymers based on Ullmann coupling.

Materials and methods

All the experiments were performed under ultra-high vacuum (UHV) conditions with base pressures below 2×10^{-10} mbar. The precursors dIB, dIB, 1,4-dichlorobenzene (dCB), 1-bromo-4-chlorobenzene (BCB) and 1-bromo-4-iodobenzene (BIB), shown in

Figure 2, were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, and were deposited through a leak valve onto Cu(110) (MaTeck GmbH), with the substrate held at room temperature (RT). All experiments were performed starting from a saturated monolayer coverage. The substrate was prepared by repeated cycles of Ar⁺ sputtering and annealing. Scanning tunneling microscopy (STM) was performed in constant-current mode using an Omicron VT-STM, and the bias voltages are measured from the tip to the sample. STM images were analyzed using WSxM,³⁶ and were treated for plane subtraction, line-by-line flattening, contrast enhancement, and were corrected based on the known lattice parameters of the substrate. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), fast-XPS and near edge X-ray absorption fine structure (NEXAFS) spectroscopy measurements were performed at the ALOISA beamline of the Elettra synchrotron-radiation facility in Trieste (Italy). XPS experiments were performed in normal emission geometry, with a 4° grazing incidence of linearly polarized radiation, and using a home-built hemispherical electron analyzer equipped with a multichannel plate (MCP) detector. The C 1s, Br 3d and Cl 2p core levels were measured at a photon energy of 390 eV with an overall energy resolution of 200 meV. The I 3d peak was measured at a photon energy of 750 eV with an overall energy resolution of 300 meV. The fast-XPS maps of C 1s were acquired by increasing the sample temperature from RT to 230 °C with a heating rate of 0.2 °C/s, using a radiative heating element behind the sample. Every line of each map is a snapshot of the C 1s peak, taken with a rate of one spectrum per second at a photon energy of 390 eV and pass energy set to 30 eV (overall energy resolution of ~350 meV). The NEXAFS C K-edge spectra were recorded in partial electron yield by means of a channeltron equipped with a filtering grid biased at -240 V in order to reject the tail of secondary electrons. The photon energy resolution was set to 100 meV. In order to calibrate the photon energy scale, the drain current on the last refocusing mirror of the beamline was measured along with the C K-edge, and subsequently calibrated back to reference data. The C-K spectrum acquired from the clean Cu(110) surface was used to normalize the spectra from surfaces containing

the molecular layers. Polarization dependent measurements were performed by rotating the sample about the beam axis, changing the angle (θ) of the surface with respect to the polarization vector from Transverse Magnetic (almost p-polarization) to Transverse Electric (s-polarization) geometry, while keeping the grazing photon incidence angle fixed at 6° (see Ref. [FLOREANO2008] for details about NEXAFS geometry and calibration “*I SUGGEST REMOVING FIG S7*”).

Density functional theory (DFT) calculations were performed with the Vienna Ab-initio Simulation Package (VASP)^{37,38} installed at SciNet³⁹ supercomputer clusters of Compute Canada. DFT calculations were made using the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof approximation (PBE)⁴⁰ of the exchange-correlation potential, the projector augmented wave (PAW)^{41,42} method, and a plane-wave basis set with an energy cut off of 450 eV. Final calculations were performed using zero-damping DFT-D3⁴³ methods of Grimme, in which vdW correction for potential energy and dispersion effects are taken into account via a semi-empirical approach. The k-point sampling was restricted to the Γ point to cope with the large size of the supercells. The energy barriers for the diffusion of the halogens (Cl, Br, I) were determined by calculating the minimum energy pathways (MEPs) along [001], [1-10], [1-1-2], and [1-11] surface directions using the climbing image nudged elastic band (CI-NEB) method.^{44,45} For the initial states, the most stable geometry/location of the halogen was found to be short-bridge for Cl and Br, and hollow for I. The path of diffusion from the initial state to the nearest similar adsorption site (as final state) along four directions of the surface was calculated for each halogen. First, the structures of the reactants and products were optimized, and then we used initial guesses for the intermediate structures (16 structures) calculated by DFT, so that, at each iteration, the NEB method nudges the reaction path (atomic coordinates) towards the minimum energy geometry until convergence is reached. The 216-atom supercell used for calculating the diffusion barrier includes a five-layer thick 4×6 Cu(110) slab and a 20 Å thick vacuum region. The bottom two layers in the Cu slab were fixed throughout the NEB calculations, while all the other atomic coordinates were relaxed until all forces were smaller than 0.05 eV/Å.

Results and discussion

1) Fast-XPS and reaction overview

The on-surface Ullmann reaction is usually reported as a two-step coupling reaction,^{25,46} with the formation of an OM intermediate and surface halide byproduct in the first step, followed by formation of C-C bond in the second, *rate-limiting* step. As such, the nature of halide is not generally considered to affect the overall rate of reaction. However, as we show below, the C-C coupling step is in fact halogen-dependent (Figure 1), and chlorine-containing molecules present an additional intermediate step before forming the OM structure.

Figure 1. Reaction schemes of halobenzenes polymerization. *dBB*, *BIB* and *BCB* on $\text{Cu}(110)$ produce a two-step reaction forming an OM intermediate at RT, and polymers at higher temperatures. Precursors with Cl (*BCB* and *dCB*) present an additional step in the reaction, due to incomplete dehalogenation of Cl at RT, which results in short chains; increasing the temperature results in a complete dehalogenation, and longer chains are formed. The polymerization step of the reaction is the same for all the five precursors.

The chemical state of the different carbon species involved in the de-halogenation and polymerization processes can be identified by the measurement of the C 1s photoemission spectra, as reported in Figure S1 (MUST BE INSERTED BEFORE THAT OF FAST XPS AND NEEDS ADEQUATE LABELLING). At Room Temperature, RT, the C 1s spectra are dominated by a main peak corresponding to the four closely equivalent hydrogen saturated carbon atoms (C-C) at a binding energy of ~ 284 eV. The de-halogenated carbon atoms, which are bound to a surface Cu adatom, give their contribution at lower binding energy (~ 283.3 eV). In the case of Chlorinated molecules, the whole C 1s spectrum is shifted at higher binding energy (0.3-0.4 eV) and an additional minority component is detected at ~ 284.5 eV, which we associate with the halogenated C-Cl component. The spectrum of the *BCB* precursor also contains the shoulder at low binding energy characteristic of the Br de-halogenation. Remarkably, also in case of the doubly chlorinated molecule, *dCB*, the C-Cu component at low energy is clearly detected, thus suggesting a partial Cl de-halogenation. This is fully consistent with the measured spectra of Cl 2p reported in Fig. S2c (TO BE SHOWN HERE, PLEASE ADD LABELS TO XPS SPECTRA), where only one doublet at ~ 200 eV ($2p_{3/2}$) is observed for *BCB* while an additional doublet at much lower binding energy is observed for *dCB* (198 eV) that can be associated with Cl atoms directly bound to the Cu substrate.

The evolution from the OM to polymeric phase was examined with fast-XPS of the C 1s core level as a function of the temperature. The fast-XPS maps shown in

Figure 2 show differences for every precursor, indicating a halogen-dependent effect on the activation energy (starting temperature) and the kinetics (interval) of the corresponding reaction. All the fast-XPS maps exhibit a shift in the C 1s spectra toward higher binding energies (BE) above 140 °C. This is a signature of polymerization, and is correlated with the progressive vanishing of the C-Cu component (at 283.3 eV) and growth of the C-C component at higher BE,^{25,34} shown in Figure S1. The maps, moreover, present differences both in the C 1s BE position and time/temperature range of the polymerization process. The fast-XPS maps illustrate a trend for the five studied precursors: the reaction starts at 125 ± 2 °C for the dIB and BIB, at 175 ± 2 °C for dBB and BCB, and at 185 °C for dCB, showing that the starting temperature of the reaction increases from the iodine- to the bromine- to the chlorine-containing molecules. While for every molecule the reaction is completed within an approximately 40 °C range, the reaction for dIB proceeds across an 80 °C range (Table S1).

Figure 2. Fast-XPS measurements of C 1s during annealing of a saturated monolayer of each precursor on Cu(110) dosed at RT. The temperatures at which 10% and 90% of the polymerization reaction is completed are marked with T_{start} (green) and T_{end} (orange) lines, respectively. White arrows indicate the change in the C 1s spectra due to C-Cl dissociation.

The maps for chlorine-containing molecules present an additional transition witnessed by an intermediate core level shift towards lower BE, at about 120 °C, as highlighted by the arrows in

Figure 2, which we can ascribe to the final dissociation of the remaining C-Cl bonds. The full dehalogenation takes place below RT for C-Br and C-I bonds and therefore does not appear in the maps of for non-chlorinated precursors. The fast-XPS maps not only identify the critical temperature of the on-surface chemical reactions, but also highlight that the C-C coupling step of the reaction is halogen-dependent. For the iodine- and bromine-containing molecules, the scheme is similar to previous reports,^{25,46} where a fully dehalogenated phase of OM chains forms at RT, and remains stable up to the polymerization temperature. For chlorine-containing molecules, the RT phase, which is stable up to 120 °C, is rather associated with the incomplete dehalogenation of dCB and BCB precursors at RT. As a result, some percentage of the phenyl groups would be Cl-terminated and form short OM chains on the surface (2 to 4 phenyls long). C-Cl bond dissociation is completed at temperatures above 120 °C

Figure 2), and longer chains are formed (>20 phenylenes long). For dBB, BIB and dIB, the C-Br and C-I bonds are dissociated upon adsorption at RT on Cu(110), as can be seen from the Br 3d (Figure

S2a) and I 3d (Figure S2e) spectra, in which their $3d_{5/2}$ components at 68.3 eV and 619.5 eV, respectively, are attributed to Cu-Br^{25,26} and Cu-I bonds.¹⁶ A single chemical state was observed for I 3d at every temperature during the reaction. For Br 3d and Cl 2p, dominant states are found at $3d_{5/2}=68.3$ eV and $2p_{5/2}=198.0$ eV respectively, and additional components at higher BE were observed, at Br $3d_{5/2}=69.1$ eV and at Cl $2p_{5/2}=198.8$ eV (Figure S2). In the case of dBB and BIB, these components were present at RT, while for chlorine-containing molecules they became apparent only after annealing to 150 °C, after dehalogenation is completed (Figure S2). The extra chemical states in Br 3d and Cl 2p spectra can be tentatively attributed to different adsorption sites of the halogen within the OM structure. BIB spectra at RT exhibit a third state at Br $3d_{5/2}=70.7$ eV, attributable to a fraction of Br-C bonds still being intact at RT.

The cleavage of C-Br and C-I bonds occurs at lower temperatures, below the temperature range investigated in this study. However, it is known that the dehalogenation of dIB on Cu(110) takes place at approximately -100 °C.²⁰ Although the dissociation temperature of Br for dBB on Cu(110) is not available in literature, the study of a porphyrin containing both Br and I adsorbed on Au(111) shows that C-I bond breaks at a lower temperature than C-Br.¹⁹ This trend agrees with DFT calculated dissociation energies of iodobenzene and bromobenzene,¹⁸ and with the experimental values of gas-phase (?) dissociation enthalpy of a halo-phenyl bond: 67 ± 2 kcal/mol for C-I, 84 ± 1 kcal/mol for C-Br and 97 ± 1 kcal/mol for C-Cl.⁴⁷

2) Structural characterisation by STM

Deposition of each precursor on Cu(110) at RT results in distinctive self-assembled OM structure, which are oriented along different lattice directions, which when annealed produce poly(paraphenylene) (PPP). The OM (in the red box, Figure 3a-d) and polymer (in the blue box, Figure 3e-f) structures obtained for the five precursors as a function of the temperature are shown in Figure 3. The assignment of these phases is based on the distances between the protrusions in the STM data for OM and polymer (6.3 Å and 4.4 Å, respectively),²⁵ together with the C 1s analysis described above.

Figure 3. STM images ($20 \times 20 \text{ nm}^2$) obtained for the five precursors on Cu(110). The OM phases (a-d) are reported in the red box (blue arrows in d) indicate the $c(2 \times 2)$ iodine superstructure. BCB and dCB show two different OM phases at RT (b) and after annealing at 150°C (a). The polymer phases (e-f), formed when annealing above 200°C are presented in the blue box.

Organometallic chains: All the OM phases (Figure 3a-d) appear in two domains related by mirror symmetry with respect to the $[1-10]$ direction, are made of chains of phenylene groups interconnected through copper atoms, and stacked into a 2D structure. The OM chains are oriented along either the $[1-1\pm 1]$ directions (Figure 3a-c, dCB, BCB, dBB, BIB) or the $[1-1\pm 2]$ directions (Figure 3d, dIB), and are interdigitated by rows of protrusions, identified as halogens.^{25,48} For iodine-containing molecules, a portion of the surface is covered by the $c(2 \times 2)$ iodine reconstruction (Figure 3d). The principal directions together with the iodine superstructure are shown in Figure S3.

Higher resolution STM images of every phase for each precursor are presented in Figure 4, superimposed with the proposed structure. OM chains along the $[1-1\pm 2]$ directions are observed only for dIB, and are composed of ordered domains of long chains (limited only by the size of the terraces, defects and other domains), with a periodic strain-relieving kink every seven phenyls (Figure S4), and a surface reconstruction corresponding to the epitaxy matrices $(1, -4 | 11, 10)$ and $(1, 4 | -11, 10)$.

For the structures that produce $[1-1\pm 1]$ -oriented OMs we observe two different types of chains: *long* (for BIB) and *short* (for dBB, BCB and dCB) at RT. The short chain structures are made of a smaller number of phenyls, between two to four for BCB and dCB (Figure 3b) and exclusively three for dBB (aka ‘chevron’ phase, Figure 3c).⁴⁸ For dBB, the short chains are always Cu-terminated (Figure 4c), while for BCB and dCB, they are Cl-terminated (Figure 4d, e), as implied from the XPS spectra in Figure S2, which shows that the dehalogenation is complete for dBB, but that dechlorination is not complete for BCB and dCB. The attachment of Cl to the chain-end forces the molecular aggregate to bend upwards the terminal phenyls, resulting in an apparent projected length along the $[1-1-1]$

direction shorter than the expected length of its planar homologue (4.9 Å instead of 6.4 Å), shown in Figure S5a,b. The reduced dichroism of NEXAFS measurements support the hypothesis of partial lifting of some benzene rings (see Section 3). The RT structure for dBB is characterised by longer-range order and described by epitaxy the matrices $(1, -4 | 6, 0)$ and $(1, -1 | 4, 1)$.³⁴ An epitaxy matrix cannot be written as for BCB and dCB at RT, due to a lack of long-range order. The dBB chevron phase is stable up to the polymerization temperature (XXoC), while the chain length of BCB and dCB increases with the temperature, until the dehalogenation process is completed at 150 °C, and long OM chains formed of a higher number of phenyls (>20) are observed on the surface (Figure S5d). As was the case for BIB at RT, these chains comprise two domains along the $[1-1\pm 1]$ directions, and have a periodic strain-relieving kink every four phenyls (Figure S4) and are described by the epitaxy matrices $(2, -2 | 4, 9)$ and $(2, 2 | -4, 9)$.

The difference between the OM chain direction for dIB and that of the other molecules (BIB, BCB and dCB) can be inferred from the halogens' preferred adsorption site on a Cu(110); iodine atoms occupy hollow sites,¹⁶ while Br and Cl atoms are located at short-bridge sites (Figure S4).^{25,26,49} STM line profiles of the halogen atoms between the OM chains show that for dIB, iodine atoms are along the $[1-1\pm 2]$ directions, with a 4.4 Å periodicity and are located in hollow positions; while for the other molecules, Br and Cl atoms follow the $[1-1\pm 1]$ directions, with a 6.3 Å periodicity and are located at short-bridge positions. For BIB, Br atoms occupy the positions between the OM chains, and iodine segregate into $c(2\times 2)$ domains. We can therefore suppose that in the BIB case, Br atoms decorate the OM chains, while I atoms are segregated into the $c(2\times 2)$ domains. At the boundaries between $c(2\times 2)$ domains and OM chains, both Br and I atoms are located along the chains, with two atoms in hollow position and one atom at short-bridge position (Figure S6).

Polymer chains: The polymer phase (Figure 3e-f), is made of linear chains of π -conjugated phenyls decorated by halogen atoms. dBB and BIB exclusively produce polymers along the direction $[1-1\pm 2]$ (aka the 'diagonal' direction of the Cu(110) surface unit cell), while BCB, dCB and dIB show polymers along both the diagonal $[1-1\pm 2]$ and 'parallel' (to the Cu(110) close-packed row, $[1-10]$) directions. Iodine-containing precursors show additional $c(2\times 2)$ iodine domains. The phenyl-phenyl distance is 4.4 Å for all the polymers, a distance which is commensurate with the diagonal direction and incommensurate for parallel the parallel direction.⁴⁸ Commensurability with the surface permits diagonal polymers to grow with little to no strain penalty, and results in the formation of large islands of polymers with a short size distribution and a mean length greater than 20 phenyl units. However, the electronic properties are strictly related to the polymer length,^{13,48} and whether a particular halogen or an intermediate phase favors longer chains is therefore important for selecting the right building block.

Figure 4. STM images (a, b, c, j, k are $5 \times 5 \text{ nm}^2$, others are $2.5 \times 5.0 \text{ nm}^2$) of OM and polymeric phases observed for each precursor, superimposed with molecular structures and copper lattice directions. OM chains for dIB (a) are orientated along the $[1-1-2]$ direction, same as the direction of the polymeric chains, while all the other OM chains are along the $[1-1-1]$ direction.

3) NEXAFS and molecular orientation

NEXAFS spectra at the C K-edge as a function of the photon's polarization, reported in Figure 5, all presents two π^* transitions at RT, π_1^* and π_2^* at ~ 284.5 and ~ 288.5 eV, respectively, in agreement with our previous report on dBB²⁵ and with the case of phenyls on Cu(111).⁵⁰ These spectra show that the phenyl rings are mostly flat on the surface, supporting the orientational hypotheses derived from the STM images. The RT NEXAFS C K-edge spectra of chlorine-containing molecules show a higher tilt of the phenyl ring, according to the change in the intensity of the π^* states as a function of the polarization of incoming photons with respect to the surface normal, particularly for π_2^* resonance (black line in Figure 5), where a peak is visible when the polarization vector of the incident light is parallel to the surface ($\theta = 0^\circ$).⁵¹ This feature is not present for the non-chlorine containing molecules at RT (Figure 5a), and is consistent with some fraction of the molecules being tilted away from the surface. We additionally note the presence of a shoulder on the high-energy side of the π_1^* resonance at $\theta = 90^\circ$ (Figure 5b), a feature not observed for the other precursors. This may suggest an additional deformation of the aromatic ring, which is known to lift the degeneracy of the anti-bonding states in planar aromatics. After annealing to 150°C the intensity of the π_2^* resonance at $\theta = 0^\circ$ for dCB and BCB is strongly suppressed, and the spectra in all polarizations become qualitatively indistinguishable from the RT spectra observed for the other molecules. This is consistent with the STM data, where OM structures along the same directions are observed for all molecules but dIB. This is additionally corroborated by the XPS data, where the C 1s core level spectra for dCB and BCB at 150°C is identical to the C 1s spectra for the other molecules at RT (Figure S1). Annealing all the precursors to 230°C completely suppresses the π_2^* resonance intensity, indicating the planarity of the aromatic rings, expected for the PPP polymers (Figure 5 and S9).^{25,26,52}

Figure 5. Polarization-dependent C K-edge NEXAFS spectra for the five studied precursors; a) dBB, BIB and dIB at RT and dCB and BCB at 150 °C; b) dCB and BCB at RT; c) all precursors at 230 °C. Two spectra are reported for each sample: $\theta = 90^\circ$ (red, corresponding to TM geometry, close to p-polarization) and $\theta = 0^\circ$ (blue, TE geometry, s-polarization) with the incident radiation falling in the plane containing the sample normal and the [001] lattice direction. The vertical black line marks the π_2^* resonance in a) and b). Single spectra for each precursor are presented in Figures S8, S9.

4) dIB vs other precursors – A different reaction pathway?

The halogen-related differences between the molecules displayed in both STM and fast-XPS measurements are clear, and could be exploited to achieve a better outcome for the reaction. For example, the choice of halogen could be used to lower temperatures required for the polymerization reaction, or to obtain surfaces that are completely covered by polymers only with no segregated halogen domains. However, the underlying reasons for these differences are not obvious, and a comparison between the STM and fast-XPS data is needed to understand why the halogen plays such a role in the reaction.

In Figure S10, a comparison of fast-XPS maps and XPS spectra between dIB and dBB is presented. dBB is taken as the representative of the other bromine- and chlorine-containing molecules (BIB, BCB and dCB) because their fast-XPS maps show similar behavior for the polymerization process, both in the temperature range of the polymerization reaction (Table S1, temperature range) and in the OM chains, all along the same directions (Figure 4). We ascribe the small differences between dBB

and

Figure 2) to the different halogens, but the same reaction pathway towards polymerization is expected. Figures S10a,c show the fast-XPS maps, whereas the C 1s line profiles relative to different temperatures are reported every 20 °C in panels b,d (identical profiles have been omitted). While for dIB the shift is continuous and gradual toward higher BE values, the shift is sharp and sudden for dBB. As discussed earlier, STM images also show a clear difference between dBB and dIB structures on the surface, likely due to the fact that for dIB both polymers and OM chains are oriented along the same direction, whereas for all the other molecules this is not the case. Therefore, for dIB the coupling can happen for two monomers in an OM chain without affecting the other adjacent ones, i.e. the reaction can take place gradually, while for the other precursors a rotation is required for the phenyl-phenyl coupling, affecting the neighboring chains. As a consequence, dBB films must overcome an additional kinetic, which occurs at a temperature higher than that required to simply couple consecutive monomers.

5) Role of the halogen in the reaction

There are different ways in which the halogen could affect the reaction mechanism and the barrier energies. Here, we present two hypotheses based on the (i) effect of different diffusion energy of the halogens, and (ii) possible presence of the halogen atoms on-top of the copper atoms in the OM structure. The hypotheses are not mutually exclusive and the observed behaviour could contain contributions from both effects.

To explore the first hypothesis, NEB calculation for the diffusion of the halogens along different directions of the Cu(110) surface were performed ([001], [1-10] and [1-12]). These simulations consider the diffusion of the halogen alone and use as starting position a hollow position for I atom and a short-bridge position for Br and Cl atoms, known to be the respective preferred adsorption site for the halogens.^{49,53-55} The diffusion energies reported in Figure 6 are in line with the electronegativity of the halogen atoms, and is therefore directly related to the Cu-halogen bond dissociation energy. The trend of the diffusion energy as $I < Br < Cl$ is consistent with the starting

temperature of the reaction found in the fast-XPS maps (

Figure 2), where the polymerization of dCB start at the highest temperature and at the lower temperature for iodine-containing molecules. Unlike chlorine and bromine, the diffusion barrier for iodine along the [1-12] direction is higher than the other two directions. This could be explained by the diffusion of iodine along the [1-12] direction, which needs to pass from a stable hollow adsorption site to an on-top location on the Cu surface. Therefore, having the lower diffusion energy barriers along the other two directions, the iodine atoms can make a two-step movement, along [1-10] and [001], instead of going directly through the [1-12]. Additional information with molecular structures for important points of the paths are presented in the SI (Figure S11-14), together with the calculations for the diffusion along the [1-11] direction. We can further speculate that a lower barrier to diffusion for the halogens also facilitates monomer diffusion, thereby reducing the transition temperature. Conversely, a higher diffusion barrier for the halogens requires an overall higher temperature, as is experimentally observed.

Figure 6. a-c) DFT calculations of the minimum energy path for the diffusion of iodine, bromine and chlorine along one unit cell in the [1-10], [001] and [1-12] directions of Cu(110). For Br and Cl, the starting equilibrium position is short-bridge, while for I is hollow. d) Diffusion energies (E_a) for I, Br and Cl along [1-10], [001] and [1-12] directions of Cu(110).

The second hypothesis is connected with the halogen being integrated into portions of the OM chains, as proposed by Di Giovannantonio *et al.*^{25,26} In this work Br atoms were proposed to occupy two different positions of the unit cell of OM chains for dBB on Cu(110), four per unit cell on the short-bridge lattice site between adjacent OM chains, and four adsorbed on top of the Cu atoms forming the OM (i.e. between the phenyls). This hypothesis is based on simulated STM images, which show a better qualitative match with the experimental STM images when top Br atoms are included. To complete the polymerization reaction, the copper atoms in the OM structure need to be expelled from the chains to permit covalent binding between adjacent phenyls. If a halogen atom is present on top

of these Cu atoms, the energies involved in the polymerization reaction must depend on the type of halogen, and will result in a different temperature for the reaction depending on the type of precursor.

Conclusions and perspectives

The role of the halogen in Ullmann coupling polymerization of five 1,4-dihalobenzene precursors containing Cl, Br, and I on Cu(110) was studied by combined fast-XPS, NEXAFS and STM analysis. On one side, the nature of the halogen atom, hence the strength of its bond to carbon atoms, directly affects the critical temperature first of the dehalogenation. On the other side, the type of halogen directly affects the geometry of the OM structures obtained at RT and can drive the orientation of the polymers. In fact, i) the length of the OM chains depends on the carbon-halogen bond dissociation energy, ii) the OM structures for precursors containing Br and Cl (dBB, dCB, BCB, BIB) are aligned along the [1-11] direction, as opposed to alignment along the [1-1-2] direction for precursors containing only iodine (dIB). The OM structures follow **different reaction pathways**, exhibiting a gradual transition for dIB while the others undergo a sudden transition into PPP polymers. A key finding of this study is that the temperature range of the polymerization is directly affected by the type of the halogen, and is correlated to that halogen's diffusion energy. Our results show that the choice of halogen is not merely a reaction byproduct, but an important parameter governing the surface polymerization reaction. which needs to be taken into consideration when a-priori designing polymeric structure through Ullmann reaction.

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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